

**INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**
[ISSN: 0975-4725; CODEN(USA): IJPS00]
Journal Homepage: <https://www.ijpsjournal.com>

Review Paper

Metformin: Beyond Glycemic Control: - Molecular Mechanisms, Underlying Cardiovascular, Metabolic and Neurocognitive Protection

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ARTICLE INFO

Published: 06 Apr 2026

Keywords:

Metformin, Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus, AMP-Activated Protein Kinase (AMPK), Cardiovascular Protection, Metabolic Regulation, Neuroprotection, Pleiotropic Effects, mTOR Pathway, Gut Microbiota, Oxidative Stress, Personalized Therapy

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.19436839

ABSTRACT

Metformin is the first-line pharmacological therapy for type 2 diabetes mellitus (T2DM), with increasing evidence demonstrating benefits beyond glycemic control. This narrative review summarizes the molecular mechanisms underlying its cardiovascular, metabolic, and neurocognitive protective effects. A comprehensive literature search was conducted using PubMed, Scopus, and Google Scholar databases for studies published between 2000 and 2025. Metformin acts through both AMP-activated protein kinase (AMPK)-dependent and independent pathways. AMPK activation regulates glucose and lipid metabolism, improves endothelial function, and reduces inflammation and oxidative stress. Additionally, mechanisms such as mTOR inhibition, gut microbiota modulation, and redox balance contribute to its systemic effects. These actions are associated with improved cardiovascular outcomes, metabolic benefits, and potential neuroprotection. However, concerns including vitamin B12 deficiency, rare lactic acidosis, and inconsistent cognitive outcomes remain. Emerging approaches such as personalized therapy and combination regimens may further optimize its clinical use. In conclusion, metformin exhibits pleiotropic effects that extend beyond glucose lowering, supporting its role as a multifunctional therapeutic agent.

INTRODUCTION

1) OVERVIEW OF T2DM

Type 2 diabetes mellitus is a chronic progressive metabolic disorder characterized by persistent hyperglycemia resulting from a combination of insulin resistance and relative insulin deficiency. It

account for nearly 90-95% of all diabetic cases worldwide and represents a major global health burden. The pathophysiology of T2DM is multifactorial, involving impaired insulin signaling in peripheral tissues (muscle, liver and adipose tissue) increased hepatic glucose production β -cell dysfunction, chronic low grade

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Relevant conflicts of interest/financial disclosures: The authors declare that the research was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

inflammation, oxidative stress and altered gut micro biota. Hyperglycemia contribute to both microvascular complications (retinopathy, neuropathy, and nephropathy) and macrovascular complications (CAD, stroke and peripheral artery disease), which significantly increase morbidity and mortality.⁽¹⁾

2) ROLE OF METFORMIN

Metformin remains the first-line pharmacological therapy for T2DM unless contraindicated. It primarily reduces hepatic gluconeogenesis, enhance peripheral insulin sensitivity and improves glucose uptake in skeletal muscle. The major molecular mechanism underlying metformin action is the activation of AMP-activation protein kinase (AMPK), a key cellular energy sensor that regulates glucose and lipid metabolism.

Beyond glycemic control, metformin has demonstrated beneficial effects on body weight, lipid profile, endothelial function and inflammatory markers. Clinical and experimental studies suggest that metformin confers cardiovascular protection, reduces oxidative stress and may improve outcomes in patients with coexisting cardiovascular disease. Its long-standing clinical use, favorable safety profile, affordability and broad metabolic benefits make it a cornerstone in diabetes management.

3) CONCEPT OF PLEIOTROPIC EFFECTS

The pleiotropic effects refers to the ability of a drug to exert multiple beneficial biological actions beyond its primary intended effect. In the context of metformin, pleiotropic includes anti-inflammatory, antioxidant, anti-atherosclerotic, endothelial-protective, anti-fibrotic, possible anti-aging and anti-neoplastic properties. These effects are mediated through AMPK-dependent and AMPK-independent pathways, influencing

cellular metabolism, mitochondrial function, autophagy and inflammatory signaling cascades. Emerging evidence indicates that metformin may improve cardiovascular outcomes independently of its glucose lowering actions thereby redefining its therapeutic potential. Understanding these mechanisms is essential for expanding its clinical application and optimizing its use in high risk populations.⁽²⁾

4) AIM OF THE REVIEW

To evaluate the pleiotropic effects of metformin beyond glycemic control, focusing on molecular mechanisms and clinical implications.

OBJECTIVES

- To describe AMPK-dependent and AMPK-independent mechanism of metformin.
- To co-relate mechanistic pathway with cardio metabolic and neurocognitive outcome.
- To analyze current controversies and notifies research gaps.

METHODOLOGY

This narrative review was conducted using a comprehensive literature search of electronic databases including PubMed, Scopus, and Google Scholar. Relevant articles published between 2000 and 2025 were included.

Search terms: Metformin, AMPK, cardiovascular protection, neuroprotection, gut microbiota and mTOR pathway.

Inclusion criteria:

- Peer-reviewed articles
- English language publications
- Clinical and experimental studies relevant to metformin mechanisms

Exclusion criteria:

- Non-peer-reviewed sources
- Studies lacking mechanistic or clinical relevance.

PHARMACOKINETIC & CELLULAR UPTAKE

Metformin is a hydrophilic biguanide that exists predominantly as a positively charged cation at physiological pH. Due to its polarity it cannot freely diffuse across lipid membranes and therefore relies on specific membrane transporters for absorption, tissue distribution and elimination. Metformin is not metabolized and is excreted unchanged by the kidneys.

1) ORGANIC CATION TRANSPORTERS (OCTs)

Cellular uptake of metformin is primarily mediated by organic cation transporters (OCTs) members of the solute carrier 22 (SLC22) family. The OCT1 (SLC22A1) is highly expressed on the basolateral membrane of hepatocytes and the principal transporter responsible for hepatic uptake. The OCT2 (SLC22A2) is a predominantly expressed in renal proximal tubular cells and mediates renal proximal tubular cells and mediates renal uptake prior to excretion. The OCT3 (SLC22A3) contributes to distribution in liver, skeletal muscle and other tissues. Multi-drug and toxin extrusion proteins (MATE1 & MATE2) facilitate renal and biliary efflux. Genetic polymorphism affecting OCT1 expression or function significantly influence hepatic metformin concentration and therapeutic response, underscoring the importance of transporter-dependent pharmacokinetics.⁽³⁾

2) HEPATIC ACCUMULATION

Oral administration of metformin is absorbed in the small intestine and delivered directly to the liver via the portal circulation, where

concentrations are subsequently higher than in systemic plasma. This first-pass exposure, combined with OCT1 expression in hepatocytes results in preferential hepatic accumulation. Systemic plasma concentration typically range from 5-20 μM under therapeutic dosing, hepatic concentration may exceed plasma level several-fold due to active transport-mediated uptake (primarily via OCT1), absence of hepatic metabolism, minimal protein binding and large apparent volume of distribution (Vd). Metformin is not bio transformed by the liver, intracellular levels depends mainly on transporter activity and renal clearance rather than metabolic degradation. The selective hepatic accumulation enables effective suppression of hepatic gluconeogenesis and represents the central mechanism underlying its anti-hyperglycemia action.⁽⁴⁾

3) MITOCHONDRIAL ACCUMULATION

Metformin cationic nature and negative mitochondrial inner membrane potential create a theoretical gradient favoring mitochondrial accumulation. Various evidence suggest that only a fraction of intracellular metformin reaches the mitochondrial matrix at therapeutic concentration. Experimental studies propose that metformin directly inhibit mitochondrial respiratory chain complex I, leading to reduced ATP production and increased AMP/ATP ratio. More of the recent analyses indicate that strong complex I inhibition typically requires supratherapeutic concentrations. Metformin appears to induce mild energetic stress rather than profound respiratory inhibition. This may contributes to alteration of cellular energy balance, increased AMP/ATP ratio, activation of AMP-activated protein kinase (AMPK) and suppression of hepatic glucose production.⁽⁵⁾

AMPK-DEPENDENT MECHANISM

Metformin activation of AMP-activated protein kinase (AMPK) remains one of the most extensively studied and biological pathways. Various studies suggest that metformin induces a mild cellular energetic stress that secondarily activates AMPK, thereby orchestrating systemic metabolic adaptation. Metformin exerts a modest and reversibly inhibitory effect on mitochondrial respiratory chain complex I instead of causing profound mitochondrial dysfunction, therapeutic concentration induce partial alteration of NADH oxidation phosphorylation. This results in fine reduction in ATP generation and concomitant increase in intracellular AMP & ADP levels.

Metformin exerts a modest and reversibly inhibitory effect on mitochondrial respiratory chain complex I instead of causing profound mitochondrial dysfunction, therapeutic concentration induce partial alteration of NADH oxidation phosphorylation. This results in fine reduction in ATP generation and concomitant increase in intracellular AMP & ADP levels. This elevation may lead to AMPK activation. AMP binding to the γ -subunit of AMPK promotes conformational changes that enhance phosphorylation by kinase and protect the enzyme from de-phosphorylation. So, small mitochondrial perturbations are amplified into significant downstream metabolic signaling events.

In liver AMPK activation plays an important role in suppressing gluconeogenesis. Activated AMPK interferes with transcriptional regulators that control expression of key gluconeogenesis enzymes, thereby reducing hepatic glucose output. (AMPK) activation limits the energetic availability required for glucose synthesis, constraining gluconeogenic flux. This dual effect on gene regulation and cellular energy balance contributes substantially to metformin anti-hyperglycemia action. (AMPK) activation also induces profound shifts in lipid metabolism by phosphorylating & inhibiting acetyl-CoA

carboxylase (ACC), AMPK lowers intracellular malonyl-CoA concentrations. This reduction relieves inhibition of carnitine palmitoyl transferase-1 (CPT-1), promoting mitochondrial fatty acid and β -oxidation. (AMPK) suppresses lipogenic gene expression, decreasing triglyceride synthesis & hepatic lipid accumulation. These actions improve hepatic steatosis and enhance systemic insulin sensitivity, extending metformin's benefits beyond glucose regulation. In vascular tissues, AMPK contributes to endothelial protection. The activation leads to phosphorylation of endothelial nitric oxide synthase (e-NOS), increasing nitric oxide bioavailability and improving endothelial-dependent vasodilation. (AMPK) signaling reduces oxidative stress within endothelial cells, which helps preserve vascular homeostasis & supporting cardio-metabolic health. Inflammatory modulation represents another important AMPK-dependent effect. Activation of AMPK suppresses nuclear factor- κ B (NF- κ B) signaling pathways, leading to decreased transcription of pro-inflammatory cytokines such as (TNF- α and IL-6).⁽⁶⁾

AMPK-INDEPENDENT MECHANISMS ^(7,8,9)

(AMPK) activation has been regarded as central to metformin's pharmacological action, accumulating evidence indicates that several of its metabolic & systemic effects occur independently of AMPK signaling. The Duet al., highlights alternative pathways through which metformin exerts metabolic, intestinal & cytoprotective effects.

1) mTOR INHIBITION

Metformin also regulates mammalian target of rapamycin (mTOR) signaling through mechanisms not completely dependent on (AMPK). Since mTOR integrates nutrients and growth signals, its inhibition contributes to

improved metabolic homeostasis, reduced lipogenesis and potential anti-aging effects.

2) GUT MICRO-BIOTA MODULATION

AMPK-independent pathway involves gut microbiota modulation. Oral metformin therapy alters intestinal microbial composition, including enrichment of beneficial bacteria such as *Akkermansia muciniphila*. These changes enhance gut barrier integrity, reduce metabolic endotoxemia and improve insulin sensitivity via the gut-liver axis.

3) GLP-1 INFLUENCE

Metformin increases circulating glucagon-like peptide-1 (GLP-1) levels. This effect is partly mediated by microbiota-derived metabolites that stimulate endocrine L-cells, thereby enhancing insulin secretion and contributing to glycemic control independently of direct AMPK signaling.

4) ANTI-OXIDATIVE EFFECTS

Metformin exerts anti-oxidative effects by suppressing mitochondrial oxidative phosphorylation, thereby reducing reactive oxidative species (ROS) production. It also alters intracellular NADH/NAD⁺ redox balance contributing to decreased oxidative stress and improved oxidative stability. These redox-modulating actions help attenuate inflammation & cellular damage independently of AMPK activation.

MECHANISTIC LINK TO CLINICAL OUTCOMES

The molecular action of metformin translates into several clinically relevant outcomes. Metformin improves survival and cardiac function following ischemia, including heart failure, by enhancing mitochondrial function & activating AMPK-

and eNOS signaling, which increases nitric oxide bioavailability & reduces oxidative stress, which leads to cardiovascular protection. Clinical evidence suggests that long-term studies in overweight patients with T2DM reported reduction in diabetes-related complications, cardiovascular events and mortality with metformin therapy.

In anti-obesity effects, several clinical investigations have shown that metformin can modestly reduce body weight & waist circumference, particularly in individuals with obesity or metabolic syndrome. Potential neurocognitive protection, as metformin may influence neuronal metabolism & mitochondrial function, indicating a possible role in reducing neurodegenerative processes such as α -synuclein accumulation, which possibly reduces cognitive decline among T2DM patients. Clinical studies indicate that metformin can promote mild weight reduction through mechanisms involving enhanced GLP-1 signaling & increased GDF15 levels that regulate appetite and energy balance.⁽¹⁰⁾

CONTROVERSIES & CONFLICTING EVIDENCE ^(11, 12, 13)

1) INCONSISTENCY IN DEMENTIA OUTCOMES

The relationship between metformin use & dementia risk remains inconsistent. While several observational studies report improved cognitive outcomes or reduced dementia incidence among metformin users, others have shown neutral or even adverse cognitive effects. Differences in study design, population characteristics, treatment duration & timing of therapy initiation may contribute to these conflicting findings.

2) VITAMIN B12 DEFICIENCY

Long-term metformin therapy has been associated with vitamin B12 deficiency, with reported

prevalence ranging from approximately. 5-40% among treated patients. The risk appears to increase with higher doses & longer duration of therapy. Metformin is believed to impair vitamin B12 absorption by interfering with calcium-dependent uptake of the vitamin B12 intrinsic factor complex in terminal ileum.

3) LACTIC ACIDOSIS CONCERNS

Metformin associated lactic acidosis has been a safety concern due to its potential effect on mitochondrial respiration and lactate accumulation. Clinical evidence suggest that this complication is extremely rare and usually occurs in patients with severe comorbid condition such as renal impairment, sepsis or hypoxia. Metformin is generally considered safe with a very low incidence of lactic acidosis.

FUTURE PERSPECTIVES OF METFORMIN

(14, 15)

1) BIOMARKERS

The identification of reliable biomarkers is crucial for optimizing metformin therapy & enabling precision medicine strategies. Tumors exhibiting phosphatase and tensin homolog (PTEN) loss, liver kinase B1 (LKB1), mutations or activation of the P13K / AKT / mTOR pathway may show greater sensitivity to metformin due to its ability to disrupt cellular energy metabolism through mitochondrial complex I inhibition and AMPK activation. Metabolic biomarkers may also help predict treatment outcomes like elevated tumor lactate levels & increased lactate dehydrogenase (LDH) activity.

2) PERSONALIZED THERAPY

Personalized therapy with metformin is an emerging approach driven by the recognition of significant inter individual variability in drug

response. Pharmacogenomics studies indicates that genetic variations, particularly in drug transport & related pathways, plays a crucial role in determining efficacy and tolerance, enabling the identifications of patients who are likely to respond well, poorly or experience adverse effects. The integration of genetic data with clinical parameters and broader multi-omics approaches is expected to refine patient stratification & optimize therapeutic outcomes. Advances in pharmacokinetic - pharmacodynamics modeling and the use of large scale datasets from electronic health records and collaborative consortia may further support individual dosing and treatment selection. This might contributes to effective management of metformin on T2DM patients.

3) COMBINATION REGIMENS

Combination therapy with metformin is a key strategy in T2DM management when monotherapy is insufficient. It is commonly combined with agents such as sulfonylureas, thiazolidinedione, DPP-4 inhibitors and SGLT2 inhibitors to cause multiple pathophysiological mechanisms. Traditional combinations like (metformin + sulfonylureas) are cost-effective but it does have associated risk such as hypoglycemia and weight gain. Newer combinations like DPP-4 Inhibitors, offers advantages including lower hypoglycemic risk, weight neutrality or loss and potential cardiovascular benefits. Fixed dose combination (FDC) improves medication adherence by reducing pill burden. So, early initiation of combination therapy may provide better and more durable glycemic control.

CONCLUSION ⁽¹⁶⁾

Metformin remains the cornerstone of pharmacological management for Type 2 Diabetes Mellitus (T2DM), primarily due to its proven efficacy in reducing hepatic gluconeogenesis and

enhancing peripheral insulin sensitivity. However, this review underscores that its clinical utility extends far beyond glycemic control through a diverse range of pleiotropic effects. By modulating both AMPK-dependent and AMPK-independent pathways, metformin influences critical cellular processes including mitochondrial function, lipid metabolism, and inflammatory signaling cascades. The drug's ability to enhance nitric oxide bioavailability, reduce oxidative stress, and inhibit pro-inflammatory cytokines such as TNF- α and IL-6 provides a robust mechanistic framework for its observed cardiovascular and endothelial protective benefits. Furthermore, emerging evidence regarding gut microbiota modulation and neurocognitive protection suggests a broader therapeutic potential in managing metabolic syndrome and potentially slowing neurodegenerative decline.

While controversies persist in particularly regarding inconsistent dementia outcomes and the risk of vitamin B12 deficiency in overall safety profile and affordability of metformin reinforce its status as a vital therapeutic agent. Future advancements in pharmacogenomics and the identification of specific biomarkers (such as LKB1 mutations) promise to transition metformin therapy toward a more personalized approach, optimizing efficacy and minimizing adverse effects for high-risk populations. In summary, metformin's multifaceted molecular actions not only solidify its current role but also facilitate for its application in diverse clinical settings beyond diabetes.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The author declares no conflict of interest.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The author acknowledges institutional support.

FUNDING

No funding was received for this study.

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HOW TO CITE: Ananda Krishnan, Metformin: Beyond Glycemic Control: - Molecular Mechanisms, Underlying Cardiovascular, Metabolic and Neurocognitive Protection, *Int. J. of Pharm. Sci.*, 2026, Vol 4, Issue 4, 875-882 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19436839>

